

Breathing Bhiwandi: An Artificial Intelligence Approach to Regional Pollution Surveillance

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18217332

Abstract:

India is the world's second most populous country and the seventh largest by land area. According to IQ Air's 2020 fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) concentration data, India is the third most polluted nation, behind Bangladesh and Pakistan. This study investigates the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) to identify an increase in Bhiwandi's pollution levels. We look at current AI applications and suggest creative ways to reduce emissions, identify pollution sources, and monitor air quality. Additionally, we discuss the difficulties associated with implementing AI and provide suggestions for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers to successfully use AI in the fight against pollution. Furthermore, survey has been thoroughly investigated using this method. The reference values were obtained from the website of Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB, India). Reducing pollution through appropriate instrumentation, maintenance methods, limiting the range of polluting sources, and machine intelligence have been the subject of more discussion and case study reasoning.

Keywords: India, Artificial Intelligence, Pollution, Bhiwandi, Central Pollution Control Board.

Introduction:

The systematic observation, measurement, and assessment of the natural environment and all of its constituent parts constitute the fundamental process of environmental monitoring. Monitoring the environment's current condition and identifying any changes that can be harmful to the ecosystem or public health is its main goal (Artiola *et al.*, 2004). Traditional environmental monitoring techniques include statistical analysis, laboratory analysis, and manual sampling (Zhang, 2024). Unfortunately, these approaches have limitations, such as high costs, prolonged procedures, and poor accuracy.

The efficiency of conventional environmental monitoring techniques is constrained by several issues. The expense of using these procedures is one of the biggest obstacles. The costs associated with manual sampling and laboratory analysis are high and include skilled employees, equipment, and chemicals (Dressing *et al.*, 2016; Ditria *et al.*, 2022). Due to this, environmental monitoring programs frequently have a limited scope, employ tiny sample sizes, and fail to present a

complete picture of the state of the environment. Another major issue is how time-consuming old approaches are (Thomson *et al.*, 2011; Ceccato *et al.*, 2014; Dressing *et al.*, 2016).

Manual sampling and laboratory analysis might take weeks or even months to produce results, delaying decision-making and emergency response in the event of pollution emergencies or natural disasters. Furthermore, the accuracy of conventional environmental monitoring methods is limited by the subjectivity of human observation and the possibility of human error (Hameed *et al.*, 2017). Human interpretation required for manual sampling and laboratory analysis can lead to inconsistent data collection and processing. Furthermore, the utilization of advanced technologies and the presence of adequately trained technical personnel necessary for precise environmental monitoring are frequently impeded by cost limitations and a scarcity of qualified individuals (Cordier *et al.*, 2021).

As a result, maintaining consistent monitoring becomes difficult, especially in areas with little funding (Li *et al.*, 2020). This is

particularly noticeable in places with inadequate technology infrastructure and knowledge (Li *et al.*, 2020). In an effort to improve accessibility to areas with limited resources and increase the objectivity of results, artificial intelligence (AI) has become a vital component of environmental monitoring initiatives. The goal of artificial intelligence (AI), a branch of computer science, is to develop algorithms and computer programs that can carry out tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as sensing, thinking, learning, and decision-making (Sarker, 2021a, b).

AI can be used to examine large data sets, and it has shown promise in spotting trends and producing accurate forecasts (Duan *et al.*, 2019). Pollution detection, water and air quality monitoring, and natural disaster forecasting are only a few of the applications of AI in environmental monitoring (Subramaniam *et al.*, 2022).

This paper aims to monitor the Air Quality Index (PM_{2.5}, CO and NO₂) of Bhiwandi in pre-monsoon, monsoon and post-monsoon. Also, to evaluate the current state of AI technologies implemented in key areas of environmental monitoring. Further we also shed light on the disease profile and health problems associated with such AQIs.

Result:

Table No. 01: Air Quality Parameter in January, April, August and November 2025

Parameter	Months (Year 2025)			
	January	April	August	November
AQI	140.61	104.53	75.84	158.63
	±24.02	±15.19	±9.47	±33.14
CO (ppb)	506.93	553.26	355.06	260.90
	±139.64	±118.41	±57.88	±84.39
NO ₂ (ppb)	13.51	10.7	8.58	24.96
	±2.56	±1.95	±0.62	±7.27
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	128.29	103.24	57.25	102.36
	±11.99	±11.25	±11.20	±35.49
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	57.09	37.2	22.62	77.86
	±5.31	±6.05	±4.83	±27.65
SO ₂ (ppb)	7.35	5.96	4.22	6.03
	±1.56	±0.85	±0.61	±2.73

Methodology:

Study Area:

The pollutants of interest PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, CO and NO₂ and SO₂ were to be modeled at two locations in Bhiwandi, namely Millat Nagar and Kalher which have different characteristics. In Fig. 1, the locations Millat Nagar and Kalher are shown with blue and black location pins respectively. The distance between the two stations is around 10 km. Bhiwandi map

Data Collection:

The data was collected using the AQI application from the period of April 2025 to December 2025 from the location of Mith Pada (Bhiwandi). The standard values for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, CO and NO₂ and SO₂ was collected from Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB).

Data Analysis:

Statistical analysis of all the collected data of pre-monsoon, monsoon and post-monsoon were done. Standard deviations and mean values were obtained using MS-Excel.

Figure No. 01: Air Quality Parameter in the month of January, April, August and November 2025

The Table 1 presents the seasonal variations in air quality index across four representative months January (Winter), April (pre-monsoon), August (monsoon) and November (post-monsoon) with values expressed as mean and standard deviation. Overall air pollution is highest during winter (January) and post monsoon (November) while August shows the lowest pollution levels.

Particulate matters (PM10, PM2.5) concentrations are markedly elevated in November and January. Among gaseous pollutants CO and NO2 shows highest concentration in winter and post

monsoon. SO2 levels remain relatively low across all months.

Discussion:

The data clearly demonstrates strong seasonal influence on air quality, with monsoon condition improving air quality and winter/ post monsoon periods posing greater health risk. Vehicle traffic on both paved and unpaved roads, dust from open fields and farmlands, construction activities in and around Bhiwandi, emissions from cars, including two- and four-wheelers, heavy vehicles, buses, etc., and dust produced by windblown dust

are the main sources of various particulate and gaseous pollutants in the study area.

In recent years, it has been observed that the number of vehicles is increasing at the rate of 10%–15% per year. The SO₂ concentrations are often under compliance due to the introduction of low-sulfur fuel for all vehicles and higher efficiency norms for all industrial activities. It was found that during monsoon, the stable conditions cause poor dispersion and high concentrations of pollutants while during the summer months, stronger winds and turbulence lead to stronger dispersion and thus lead to lower pollutant concentrations.

The majority of Indian cities have seen a significant decline in air quality over the past few decades due to severe air pollution issues in many of them, including Delhi and Kolkata (Ghose *et al.*, 2005), where the air quality is over the CPCB and WHO guidelines. The majority of gaseous pollutants in Indian cities had high daily and annual average values (Dandotiya *et al.*, 2020).

Human health is impacted by air pollution in the short, medium, and long terms (Gumashta and Bijlwan, 2020). The short-term health impacts of air pollution exposure have been the subject of numerous research. Long-term effects of air pollution include lung cancer, heart issues, chronic respiratory diseases, and even harm to the brain, liver, kidneys, or nerves (Faheem *et al.*, 2021). Short-term effects include irritation of the eyes, throat, and nose as well as certain respiratory infections like pneumonia and bronchitis. In the meantime, Prabhakaran *et al.*, (2020) found that exposure to air pollution, whether short-term or long-term, increased the incidence of incident hypertension and raised blood pressure. There has also been discussion of the relationships between gaseous pollution and health effects. (Samoli *et al.*, 2008, 2013; Stafoggia *et al.*, 2013).

Higher levels of gaseous and particulate matter in the air are strongly linked to hospitalizations for respiratory and post-respiratory disorders as well as premature death in urban areas (Burnett *et al.*, 1997; Yang *et al.*, 2004). According

to Rajput *et al.* (2019), tiny particles considerably deposited in the pulmonary region, while coarse particles showed a greater mass deposition percentage in the extrathoracic region. Deeper penetration and a larger mass deposition fraction of fine particles in the PUL region are consequences of increased biomass and biofuel burning emissions during the winter and post-monsoon seasons.

In addition, irritation of the alveoli, resistance in the airways and pulmonary function, and a reduction in pulmonary capacity are among the health effects of NO₂ that have been documented for places like Agra and Taiwan (Mudgal *et al.*, 2000; Yang *et al.*, 2005; Saini *et al.*, 2008). Exposure to high SO₂ concentrations has been linked to respiratory health consequences, decreased birth rates, lower birth weights, and chronic bronchitis (Ciccone *et al.*, 1995; Dejmeek *et al.*, 2000; Rogers *et al.*, 2000). Particulate matter was found to be a more significant cause of air pollution-related mortality and morbidity than gaseous air pollutants, despite the fact that gaseous air pollutants like NO₂ and SO₂ are a growing concern for human health (Maji *et al.*, 2016).

Conclusion:

This study highlights the effectiveness of artificial intelligence based approaches of air quality surveillance in Bhiwandi. Using CPCB and AQI data AI assisted analysis successfully identified seasonal variations in key pollutants with higher concentrations of PM 2.5, PM 10, CO, NO₂ and SO₂ in winter and post monsoon periods and improved air quality during the monsoon. Particulate matters emerged as the major contributor to pollution-related health risk. The findings emphasized that AI – driven monitoring can overcome limitations of conventional methods by enabling efficient, continuous and data driven methods. Integrating AI with appropriate policy measures and emissions control strategies can significantly support pollution reduction and public health protection.

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